

ANALYSIS OF FATIGUE FAILURE OF CONNECTING ROD USED IN A LIGHT COMMERCIAL VEHICLE (LCV) THROUGH FEA

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ABSTRACT:

The main objective of this study was to investigate the design, mass and cost reduction of connecting rod made up of structural steel for 970 cc four cylinder four stroke engines. Every stroke of the engine subjected to its adjacent components to cyclic loading that pulls and pushes the connecting rod and crankshaft. The design of the Connecting rod can be done in a justifiable manner if an attempt is made to identify the effects of the operating loads on the component in the form of the type of stress induced with its peak value and the location of these stresses over the component. This study consists of two major sections, Finite Element Analysis and Optimization for design and mass reduction.

In this paper, existing connecting rod is been optimized with change of various design parameters for I- Section followed by 3-D CAD- modeling using Solid Works. Second order Tetrahedron mesh is been carried out in Hypermesh. 3-D finite element analysis is planned to be carried out by virtue of static stress analysis and followed by fatigue life prediction of Connecting rod using Ansys Workbench. Alternatives for Design would be suggested while attempting to modify the geometry of the Connecting rod by changing the different parameters.

KEYWORDS: Light commercial vehicle, connecting rod, ANSYS, FEM, Weight optimization.

INTRODUCTION:

The automobile engine connecting rod is a high volume production, critical component. It connects reciprocating piston to rotating Connecting rod, transmitting the thrust of the piston to the Connecting rod. Every vehicle that uses an internal combustion engine requires at least one connecting rod depending upon the number of cylinders in the engine. Connecting rods for automotive applications are typically manufactured by forging from either wrought steel or powdered metal. They could also be cast. However, castings could have blow-holes which are detrimental from durability and fatigue points of view. The fact that forgings produce blow-hole-free and better rods gives them an advantage over cast rods. Between the forging processes, powder forged or drop forged, each process has its own pros and cons. Powder metal manufactured blanks have the advantage of being near net shape, reducing material waste. However, the cost of the blank is high due to the high material cost and sophisticated manufacturing techniques with steel forging, the material is inexpensive and the rough part manufacturing process is cost effective. Bringing the part to final dimensions under tight tolerance results in high expenditure for machining, as the blank usually contains more excess material so in order to reduce the material cost and thus for production cost it is better to optimize the weight or volume. And thus due to its large volume production, it is only logical that optimization of the connecting rod for its weight or volume will result in large-scale savings.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED:

The methodology carried out in order to overcome the above problem would be studying & identifying the design of the existing Connecting rod, carrying out various geometric iterations of the I-Section. Building the solid model in Solid Work followed by carrying out meshing in Hyper mesh and Static Structure analysis along with fatigue life prediction in Ansys Work bench. Only the critical areas of connecting rod would be studied for the work and suitable recommendation can be find out while concluding the work. Practicality of the recommended solution pertaining to the cost and ease of deployment would be considered while suggesting the variants for design.

Figure 1: Methodology of Project

INPUT DATA:

ENGINE SPECIFICATIONS:

Specifications of Connecting rod:

Displacement : 970 CC

Max. Power : 103 kW@3750rpm

Gear Ratio : Max. 1.409 or Min. 2.268

MATERIAL:

The Structural Steel used for Connecting rods is high grade steel alloy which has the following composition and physical properties:

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION:

Carbon	0.15-0.30%
Chromium (Cr)	0.8-0.9%
Molybdenum (Mo)	0.08-0.25%
Silicon (Si)	0.40%
Manganese	0.50-1.70 %
Sulphur	0.035% max
Copper (Cu)	0.20 %
Nickel (Ni)	0.30-1.50 %

Table 1: Physical Properties of Original Connecting Rod

Density	7850kg m ⁻³
Tensile strength	460 MPa
Yield strength	250 MPa
Young's modulus	200000MPa

Table 2: Description of Original Connecting Rod

Sr. No.	Parameters	Default value (mm)
1	Connecting rod length	360
2	Crank end inner diameter	55
3	Crank end outer diameter	90
5	Piston Pin end inner diameter	30
6	Piston Pin end outer diameter	50
7	Shank Thickness	12

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

While implementing this project an analysis of four different connecting rods has been done including existing rod. Ansys and FEM analysis are presented below for four types of connecting rod.

Figure 2: Ansys analysis of existing rod

After finite element modeling we performed static analysis. The various individual loads acting on the connecting rod were used for finding the structural behavior of connecting rod and stress distribution was obtained. The loads included static compressive load and static tensile load. Analysis of connecting rod is performed under extreme loading Condition.

1. Small end Compressive loading and bigger end fixed.

For the current study we have analyzed connecting rod under static load conditions. The loads included static compressive load. For static analysis one of the ends of the connecting rod is fixed and other is given standard loads to determine stresses and deflection. The connecting rod has been separately analyzed for the compressive load due to gas pressure. The study also indicates that the buckling is important design factor that must be taken into account during the design process.

On the basis of the stress and strain measurements performed on the connecting rod, closed agreement has been found with applied static loads. Questions are naturally raised in light of such a complex structural behavior, such as: Does the peak load at the end of the connecting rod represents the worst case loading? Under the effect of axial load can one expect higher stresses than the experienced under axial load alone?

So this chapter discusses, such as how loads and constraints have been applied, weather connecting rod is safe against buckling, stress distribution along the length of the connecting rod and deflection in connecting rod.

CONCEPT OF WEIGHT OPTIMIZATION:

The process in which weight of the component reduced, maximum stresses at critical locations reduced and cost of the component reduced without minimizing the fatigue strength of the component is called as weight optimization. The optimization study performed on Connecting rod was not the mathematical optimization process. Design variables as a tool for Connecting rod optimization process. In the geometry optimization process the shape of the component remains same only size is modified. In the Connecting rod optimization mass reduction, cost reduction and improving fatigue performance using alternative materials and considering manufacturing aspects based on FEA simulation and dynamic load analysis. In the geometric optimization Connecting rod web thickness, web geometry, increasing inner hole diameter and their depth simulated to reduce the weight and final cost of the product.

CONSTRAINTS:

The following dimensions were not changed in the optimization process of Connecting rod.

1. Piston pin diameter remains constant.
2. Crank pin diameter remains constant.
3. Length between centers constant.
4. Material remains same.

DESIGN VARIABLES:

In the optimization process some parameters and dimensions should be changed are called as design variables. There is various design variables could be changed and considered in the Connecting rod optimization process they are as follows.

1. Thickness of the Connecting rod web.
2. Changes in pin fillet
3. Internal and external fillet radii of shank.

MODIFICATION -I OF CONNECTING ROD MODEL:

The modified design of Connecting rod is modeled using SOLIDWORKS software. Geometry provided had to clean and following modifications were done.

- a) Model was cleaned up and was made symmetric.
- b) Duplicate surfaces were removed.
- c) Irregular surfaces were removed & replaced with proper surfaces.
- d) Connectivity with neighboring surfaces was maintained.
- e) Changing Connecting rod web thickness 12mm to 10mm.
- f) We did small fillets as 1mm & big fillets as 8mm.
- g) Lubricating hole as 3mm diameter.

Because of this modification actual weight which was 10.12 kg was reduced to 9.47 kg.

Figure 3: Ansys analysis of modification – I

MODIFICATION – II

Figure 4: Ansys analysis of modification – II

Connecting rod was modeled using solid work software and all the specification was accordingly followed the relevant modification. The web thickness changes to 11 mm & small fillets as 2 mm

& big fillets as 9mm, where as the Connecting rod diameter and length is considered to be same as that of original Connecting rod design. The following images show the modified 3D modeling of Connecting rod.

A static structural analysis is carried out with the given loading condition in the ANSYS solver. Preprocessing of Connecting rod is done by using HYPERMESH software. Where the 3D tetrahedral mesh is done and the input deck is prepared for ANSYS solver. The result is shown below.

It is been observed that under compressive load, the critical regions are the crank end transition, pin end transition and the web at the crank end. Thus plot gives us the general idea of the stress variation on the connecting rod. The meshed model has number of nodes 3767855 and number of elements are 2520485. The static loads for which these stresses are plotted is a compressive load of 18 KN. From static analysis of Modified Connecting rod-II it is clear that when a force 18 KN is applied on the Connecting rod at piston pin location, we found that, the Maximum Deflection is 0.0154 mm and Maximum stress is 24.22 MPa. The Maximum principle stress distribution in connecting rod under compression which is 13.00MPa & The Minimum principle stress distribution in connecting rod under compression which is 1.44 MPa.

MODIFICATION- III

Connecting rod was modeled using solid work software and all the specification was accordingly followed the relevant modification. The web thickness changes to 13 mm & small fillets as 3mm & big fillets as 10mm, where as the Connecting rod diameter and length is considered to be same as that of original Connecting rod design. The following images show the modified 3D modeling of Connecting rod.

Connecting rod was modeled using solid work software and all the specification was accordingly followed the relevant modification.

A static structural analysis is carried out with the given loading condition in the ANSYS solver. Preprocessing of Connecting rod is done by using HYPERMESH software. Where the 3D tetrahedral mesh is done and the input deck is prepared for ANSYS solver.

It is been observed that under compressive load, the critical regions are the crank end transition, pin end transition and the web at the crank end. Thus plot gives us the general idea of the stress variation on the connecting rod. The meshed model has number of nodes 3753355 and number of elements are 2516069. The static loads for which these stresses are plotted is a compressive load of 18 KN. From static analysis of Modified Connecting rod-III it is clear that when a force 18 KN is applied on the Connecting rod at piston pin location, we found that, the Maximum Deflection is 0.01374 mm and Maximum stress is 19.16 MPa. The Maximum principle stress distribution in connecting rod under compression which is 12.73MPa & The Minimum principle stress distribution in connecting rod under compression which is 1.45 MPa.

Figure 5: Ansys Analysis for modification –III

CALCULATION OF VARIOUS PARAMETERS FOR ALL FOUR CASES:

Table 3: Calculation of various parameters for all four cases

Parameter	Design Calculation of Existing Connecting Rod	Modification -I of Connecting Rod Model	Modification -II of Connecting Rod Model	Modification -III of Connecting Rod Model
Total volume of connecting rod model,	$V_{tot} = 1287898.089 \text{ m}^3$	$V_{tot} = 1206369.427 \text{ m}^3$	$V_{tot} = 1232356.688 \text{ m}^3$	$V_{tot} = 1256560.51 \text{ m}^3$
Mass density of connecting rod model,	$\rho = 7.85 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg/m}^3$	$\rho = 7.85 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg/m}^3$	$\rho = 7.85 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg/m}^3$	$\rho = 7.85 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg/m}^3$
Total weight of connecting rod model	10.12 kg	9.47 kg	9.67 kg	9.864 kg
Gas Force	$F_p = 18 \text{ KN}$	$F_p = 18 \text{ KN}$	$F_p = 18 \text{ KN}$	$F_p = 18 \text{ KN}$
Moment of Inertia (Ixx)=	724032 mm^4	349162.69 mm^4	510496.2283 mm^4	9985252.937 mm^4
Moment of Inertia (Iyy)	226368 mm^4	109162.69 mm^4	159112.2283 mm^4	310388.9367 mm^4

Section Modulus:	11318.4mm ³	5458.1345mm ³	7955.6114mm ³	39834.1174mm ³
Slenderness Ratio	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.2
Von-Mises Stress Calculations: CASE-I	$\sigma_x = 11.36$ $\sigma_y = 0$	$\sigma_x = 16.4684$ $\sigma_y = 0$	$\sigma_x = 14.6568$ $\sigma_y = 0$	$\sigma_x = 10.4272$ $\sigma_y = 0$
Von-Mises Stress Calculations: CASE –II	$\sigma_x = 11.30$ $\sigma_y = 17.091$ $\sigma_v = 15.05$	$\sigma_x = 16.42$ $\sigma_y = 35.4419$ $\sigma_v = 30.72$	$\sigma_x = 14.6155$ $\sigma_y = 24.2411$ $\sigma_v = 21.14$	$\sigma_x = 10.396$ $\sigma_y = 12.4256$ $\sigma_v = 11.5456$
Buckling load	17402.147	260560.4662	223413.7781	420229.9896
Fatigue Life Calculation	$\sigma_a = 7.525$ MPa Mean Stress $\sigma_m = 7.525$ MPa for forged steel $S_e' = 230$ MPa Endurance limit $S_e = 184$ MPa From modified goodman line $n = 17.5438$	$\sigma_a = 15.3$ MPa Mean Stress $\sigma_m = 15.3$ MPa for forged steel $S_e' = 230$ MPa Endurance limit $S_e = 184$ MPa From modified goodman line $n = 8.58$	$\sigma_a = 10.5$ MPa Mean Stress $\sigma_m = 10.5$ MPa for forged steel $S_e' = 230$ MPa Endurance limit $S_e = 184$ MPa From modified goodman line $n = 12.51$	$\sigma_a = 5.77$ MPa Mean Stress $\sigma_m = 5.77$ MPa for forged steel $S_e' = 230$ MPa Endurance limit $S_e = 184$ MPa From modified goodman line $n = 22.7842$
Fatigue Strength	Modified Goodman line $S_f = 7.650$ MPa Finite Life $N = 6.927226 \times 10^{33}$ Cycles	Modified Goodman line $S_f = 15.83$ MPa Finite Life $N = 2.069 \times 10^{27}$ Cycles	Modified Goodman line $S_f = 10.74$ MPa Finite Life $N = 5.982 \times 10^{30}$ Cycles	Modified Goodman line $S_f = 5.8432$ MPa Finite Life $N = 1.7456 \times 10^{36}$ Cycles

Figure 6: Comparison of deformation.

Figure7: Comparison of Von-Mises Stress.

Figure 8: Comparison of Mass.

CONCLUSIONS:

1. Original Connecting rod shows the maximum deflection of 0.01419 mm.
2. Original Connecting rod shows the Maximum Von-Mises stress is observed to be 27.29 MPa near the piston pin end.
3. The minimum life predicted by simulation is about 6.9E33 cycle for the original Connecting rod design which shows the infinite life of connecting rod.
4. The mass of original Connecting rod is 10.12K g
5. Selecting Modification I as a best Optimized Connecting rod because the maximum Von-Mises stress is to be 32.31 MPa which is less than the material yield stress.
6. Modified I Optimized Connecting rod shows the maximum deflection of 0.01657 mm which is well within the permissible limit.
7. The minimum life predicted by simulation is about 2.069E27 cycle for the Modified-I Connecting rod design.
8. The mass of Modified-I Connecting rod is 9.47 Kg.
9. Material and cost saving is 0.65Kg and 250/- per piece respectively. Hence we have saved 6.5% of each.

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